

OCEAN:ICE News – April 2024

OCEAN:ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN:ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System.

OCEAN:ICE News is a monthly newsletter updating about the project's progress, results, and other exciting events! Be sure to follow us on LinkedIn to stay informed.

Welcome!

Welcome to the April's OCEAN:ICE News! We're thrilled to keep you updated on the latest from the world of OCEAN:ICE.

This month is a special one for OCEAN:ICE, as we are welcoming a new partner to the project. Read on to learn all about the National Antarctic Science Center of Ukraine (NASC) joining OCEAN:ICE. Also, we're introducing you to April's researcher in the spotlight, informing you about the submission of project's milestones, engaging Climate Coffees, and providing you with a chance to learn about the representation of OCEAN:ICE at 2024 UN Ocean Decade Satellite Event 'Monitoring the Ocean', in case you couldn't attend it or wish for a recap. Moreover, if you read on, April's OCEAN:ICE News will help you to stay informed about where you can find OCEAN:ICE in action at various upcoming events.

Enjoy exploring this month's updates, and we look forward to bringing you more news in May!

The National Antarctic Science Center of Ukraine Joins OCEAN:ICE

OCEAN:ICE is delighted to welcome a new partner to OCEAN:ICE this month. [The National Antarctic Science Center of Ukraine \(NASC\)](#) joins OCEAN:ICE and helps to make us a truly circum-Antarctic project. Under the widening access programme of Horizon Europe, NASC has joined as full partner and will contribute both fieldwork and deployment of ocean floats as well as meteorological observations and analysis of extreme events around the peninsula. The key task of NASC is, using the logistical support of its research vessel 'Noosfera', to build a bridge between practical measurements in the ocean, using ocean floats, and theoretical modelling, such as state-of-the-art particle tracking model, under ice shelves. Some of you may already know our new colleagues via other Horizon Europe projects that NASC also participates in, but we hope to profile the NASC team in next month's newsletter and welcome them in person to the annual project meeting in Copenhagen, 23-25 September 2024.

[Evgen Dykyi](#), the director of NASC: *'Now humanity faces a difficult time: when some act to solve global problems such as climate change and relevant sea level rise, others call us back to dark times full of wars, violence and authoritarianism. Ukraine is now on the front line of this battle of visions for the future. So even in these hard times for us it is really important to contribute to the world science and solution of global problems and we are happy to have this new opportunity to cooperate, share and investigate together within OCEAN:ICE'.*

Researcher in the Spotlight: Povl Abrahamsen

We are continuing with our article series 'Researcher in the Spotlight'. Check out our latest feature on [Povl Abrahamsen](#), a Physical Oceanographer at [British Antarctic Survey](#).

Read Povl's interview [here](#).

Stay tuned for more features from our Research Team in OCEAN:ICE.

Catching up on the Latest OCEAN:ICE Activities

OCEAN:ICE Milestones MS8 and MS9 Submitted

OCEAN:ICE has recently hit a couple of milestones:

- MS8 'IEnKS Algorithm for Initialising Coupled Ice - Ocean Models'
- MS9 'Deployment of Moorings in South Sandwich Trench'

The progress and results of OCEAN:ICE are published in deliverables and milestone reports.

In order to keep up with the OCEAN:ICE deliverables and milestones, visit our [website](#) and stay tuned on our social media channels.

The screenshot shows two tweets from OCEAN:ICE (@OCEANICE_EU). The first tweet, dated 12/11/2020, announces Milestone 8: 'IEnKS Algorithm for Initialising Coupled Ice - Ocean Models' has been published. The second tweet, dated 12/11/2020, announces Milestone 9: 'Deployment of Moorings in South Sandwich Trench' has been published. Both tweets include a link to the full milestone report: [doi.org/10.5281/zenodo...](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5281)

The screenshot shows the OCEAN:ICE website navigation bar with links for About, Knowledge Hub, News, Events, Results, and Contact. Below the navigation bar is a blue banner with the text 'Deliverables and Milestones' and a sub-header 'The progress and results of OCEAN:ICE are published in deliverables and milestone reports.'

Deployment of moorings in South Sandwich Trench (MS9)

This report summarises the work performed, and reasons for the delay to the milestone. The mooring deployment is described in more details in the full cruise report for FV Argos Georgia voyage SS24, which will be submitted to the British Oceanographic Data Centre (BODC), to be linked from https://www.bodc.ac.uk/resources/inventories/cruise_inventory/report/18630/ Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10955998>

OCEAN:ICE at 2024 UN Ocean Decade Satellite Event ‘Monitoring the Ocean’

On the 8th of April 2024 in Barcelona, at [the Institut de Ciències del Mar](#) and online, OCEAN:ICE collaborated alongside many [Horizon Europe](#) funded projects, such as [TipESM](#), [ObsSea4Clim](#), [Arctic PASSION](#), [Group for High Resolution Sea Surface Temperature \(GHRST\)](#) for the [2024 UN Ocean Decade Conference](#) Satellite Event ‘Monitoring the Ocean: Panel Discussion and Networking Event’ and a photo exhibition on beautiful images from fieldwork with inputs from [Danish Meteorological Institute](#), [Scottish Association For Marine Science](#), [European Polar Board](#), [British Antarctic Survey](#) and many more.

[Chiara Bearzotti](#) (EU Grant Project Manager, [Danish Meteorological Institute](#)) represented OCEAN:ICE in the panel discussion delivering a presentation ‘Complementarity of ocean observations (in situ) for monitoring the ocean from the ocean’.

Three photos taken by OCEAN:ICE project member, [Povl Abrahamsen](#) (Physical Oceanographer, [British Antarctic Survey](#)), were showcased in the photo exhibition.

Read more about the representation of OCEAN:ICE at 2024 UN Ocean Decade Satellite Event ‘Monitoring the Ocean’ on our [website](#).

The poster features a dark teal background with a colorful rainbow bar at the top. On the left, there is a circular inset image showing a harbor with many boats and a historic building. The text is arranged in a clean, modern layout with white and yellow colors.

2024 OCEAN DECADE CONFERENCE

DELIVERING THE SCIENCE WE NEED FOR THE OCEAN WE WANT
10-12 APRIL 2024
BARCELONA, SPAIN

As part of the Ocean Decade Week (8-12 April 2024)

2024 Ocean Decade Satellite Event

Monitoring the Ocean
Panel Discussion and Networking Event

April 8th, 15:00
Institut de Ciències del Mar (ICM)
Pg. Marítim de la Barceloneta, 37, Ciutat Vella, 08003
Barcelona, Spain

2021 United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development
2030

Climate Coffees

Since its relaunch the [Climate Coffee series](#) has been in full swing. If you've missed any of the recent ones, don't worry, you may catch up [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Upcoming Events

OCEAN:ICE at the EGU General Assembly 2024

OCEAN:ICE project members, [Violaine Coulon \(ULB\)](#), [work package 4](#), and [Anna Olivé Abelló \(IGE\)](#), [work package 2](#), will present their work at the [EGU General Assembly 2024](#).

Vio's poster '[Constraining Projections of Future Freshwater Fluxes from Antarctica](#)' will be displayed on Monday 15 April 2024 between 10:45 and 12:30 CEST in Hall X5 and Anna's poster '[Revisiting the Iceberg Thickness Distribution in Southern Ocean Simulations](#)' on Tuesday 16 April 2024 between 16:15 and 18:00 CEST in Hall X4.

Learn more about OCEAN:ICE presence at the EGU 2024 on our [website](#).

The poster features a background of abstract, blurred blue and purple patterns. In the top left corner is the OCEAN:ICE logo, which includes a globe icon and the text 'OCEAN:ICE'. In the top right corner is the EGU General Assembly logo, featuring a circular arrow icon and the text 'EGU General Assembly'. The main title 'OCEAN:ICE at EGU' is centered in large, bold, white font. Below the title, the dates and location '14 - 19 April 2024 | Vienna & Online' are displayed in a smaller white font. In the bottom left corner is the European Union flag. To the right of the flag, the following text is written in white: 'OCEAN:ICE is funded by the European Union, Horizon Europe Funding Programme for research and innovation under grant agreement Nr. 101060452 and by UK Research and Innovation'.

OCEAN:ICE at EGU

14 - 19 April 2024 | Vienna & Online

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OCEAN:ICE Storyline Meetings

In OCEAN:ICE, we run storyline meetings which we use as a communication tool so that the work packages in the project can talk together across the following cross-cutting themes:

- Deep uncertainty in freshwater fluxes
- Bottom water and lower cell
- Oxygen isotope exploitation
- The role of pole(s) in the global climate system

Coming up in April, the cross-cutting theme 'The role of pole(s) in the global climate system' will be meeting on the 29th of April 2024 at 11:00 CEST. The [University of Reading's Robin Smith](#), will be leading the meeting.

In May, another cross-cutting theme 'Deep uncertainty in freshwater fluxes' will be meeting on the 2nd of May 2024 at 15:00 CEST. The meeting will be led by [Université libre de Bruxelles' Frank Pattyn](#).

This series of storyline meetings contribute to OCEAN:ICE's [milestones](#).

Happening in Spring

OCEAN:ICE will be at these upcoming events. Will you also be there? Let us know!

- 14-19 April 2024, [EGU General Assembly](#), Vienna & online
- 17-19 April 2024, [Observing the Dynamics of the Southern Ocean: Present Challenges and Future Strategies Workshop](#), San Diego & online
- 7-18 May 2024, [Southern Ocean Summer School](#), Cargese
- 27-29 May 2024, [IMDIS](#), Bergen & online

Do you know of any exciting events that OCEAN:ICE should be a part of? Shoot us a mail at oceanice.eu@gmail.com.

Are you following us on Social Media?

Stay up to date with OCEAN:ICE on our following channels:

www.ocean-ice.eu

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/euoceanice/>

https://twitter.com/OCEANICE_EU

<https://fediscience.org/@OceanIceEU>

<https://www.facebook.com/OCEANICEEU/>

Who is OCEAN:ICE?

OCEAN:ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System. OCEAN:ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN:ICE focus on understanding how the Antarctic ice sheet and the surrounding Southern Ocean influence our global climate and reduce the level of uncertainty around how much the Antarctic ice sheet will melt in the coming centuries. OCEAN:ICE considers the critical role of feedbacks between ocean circulation, ice sheet change and tipping points and the global climate. [Find out more](#)

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